

SLOWING DOWN AS A (ROLE) MODEL

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“Really? Are you sure about that?”

Last week I had the opportunity to visit one of my new academic soul-mates, Alina Rusu at University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine, Cluj-Napoca, Romania. Alina leads a group that studies human-animal interactions, especially in the context of service animals. She also has a strong interest in community engagement, and works with the public frequently. We met first through the COST action I’m chairing a working group in on [Societal impacts of understanding animals’ affective states](#) and very quickly figured out that we would both be at the [European Association of Service Learning in Higher Education](#) meeting in October. With so many shared interests, when a work visit opportunity arose for me to go to Cluj-Napoca and meet Alina’s group, I was more than excited to do so!

And then the search for travel started. This year has had a lot of travel involved; leading this working group means lots of inspiring events all over Europe, which both makes me happy... and worries me. I made the decision several years ago that the 1 or 2 day trips for work to far-off places can be very useful and very occasionally cause a substantial shift in my thinking, or open up a completely new network of people that I otherwise wouldn't have known... but the environmental impact is just too high. This has gained attention in recent years in academia in a number of publications (Quinton, 2020) and [policies, including at my own university](#). A recent paper by Kapoor and colleagues set out to calculate the environmental cost of conferences in their field, and the conclusion is: a lot (Kapoor et al., 2025).

So, whenever possible, I take the train these days. And when not possible, I seriously think about how important the travel really is. Can it be done online? Will I really get a chance to talk with people, rather than wandering a huge meeting venue? And: I talk about going places by train, and why. Not to shame people out of flying, but to show that there really are alternatives.

In this case, Cluj-Napoca is literally three trains away. Utrecht to Munich, Munich to Budapest, Budapest to Cluj-Napoca. Yes, it is a two day trip that involved an overnight stay in Budapest- though there are actually night trains with sleeper cars on this route, I decided to stick with day trains this time. It was a great trip, and I had all kinds of time to catch up on (work and non-work) reading, to catch up on my Philosophy of Law online class (a Bachelors-level class from the Dutch Open University, which is fantastic; taking a Bachelors class as an educator is a humbling experience and a topic for another day) and look at the fantastic scenery of Transylvania- which also link to the idea of Slow Science talked about in “Another Science is Possible” (Stengers & Muecke, 2018) and more recently by Utrecht colleagues (Meijer & Webster, 2025). So when people kept asking me “Are you sure about this?” when I said I was taking the train to Romania, yes, I’m sure.

I wrote a bit about [where I traveled to this year and tips and tricks for long-distance train here](#) and [Dan Stowell wrote a really nice blog entry with emissions calculations for his travel that is linked to here](#). And both of us conclude that while perfect may not be possible, making a big difference certainly is. This is also not for everyone- when I was single parenting small ones travel was out in general, let alone adding extra days to travel- but now, for me, this is something concrete I *can* do, which is heartening in the face of all the things I can’t do. And a way to hopefully be a role model about some aspects of being an academic, part of the [role model mosaic that Isabella Spaans so beautifully writes about](#) (Spaans et al., 2023).

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